

Four pathways to final investment decision: A data-driven perspective on clean hydrogen in Africa

Executive Summary

Clean hydrogen is poised to become a critical pillar of the global energy transition, yet actual investment and project deployment remain highly uneven across regions. While more than 2,600 clean hydrogen projects are currently tracked worldwide according to the International Energy Agency (IEA), only a small share has progressed to final investment decision (FID) or operation, and these are overwhelmingly concentrated in the Global North and China. In Africa, only eight of 122 projects have reached FID, underscoring a substantial maturity gap.

This report explains these differences through a data-driven analysis of global project success factors. Using the IEA hydrogen project database enriched with AI-assisted research, the study identifies four distinct success pathways: export-oriented large-scale projects; vertically integrated sponsor—offtaker models; mid-scale projects situated in favorable economic environments; and small-scale, domestically oriented projects driven by industrial growth and climate-related opportunity.

*: Share of analyzed projects in cluster.

Africa's announced projects show a heavy bias toward large, export-oriented models, with 89% of projects in North Africa and 76% in Sub-Saharan Africa targeting export markets. This approach increases exposure to offtake uncertainty—one of the most significant barriers to securing investment. Limited value-chain integration and weaker economic and institutional environments compound these challenges. Despite vast renewable energy resources and strong industrial growth potential, African projects often lack the domestic anchors and risk-mitigation structures characteristic of successful global projects.

A key opportunity lies in building stronger domestic or regional anchors, particularly around established demand centers such as fertilizers. Exploring local or regional offtake options can substantially lower commercial risk by reducing reliance on distant and uncertain export markets. Complementing such strategic project design with concessional finance and targeted financial support instruments also plays a decisive role. These mechanisms are essential to de-risk clean hydrogen projects and mobilize the capital required to reach FID, especially during costly early development stages.

However, the financing landscape further illustrates the continent's structural constraints. Africa currently has €4 billion in targeted financial support for clean hydrogen, compared to USD 222 billion (€192 billion) available to the rest of the world. In addition, only 20% of these funds available to African projects have been disbursed, highlighting a disconnect between available capital and project readiness. Funding is highly concentrated—78% originates from EU institutions and governments, particularly through the European Investment Bank, the EU Global Gateway, and German instruments such as H2Global (€887 million committed)ⁱ and KfW's PtX Platform. Although multilateral actors such as the Climate Investment Funds (CIF) and national investment funds in Egypt, Namibia, and South Africa contribute additional support, these remain small relative to needs.

Based on the data-driven analysis of success pathways for clean hydrogen projects and the complementary analysis of the financial landscape in Africa, the report identifies targeted, actionable recommendations to accelerate project development:

- Establishing **stronger domestic anchors**—through regional value-chain development, industrial integration, and local offtake—will be key to reducing commercial risk and enhancing long-term socio-economic benefits.
- African countries should **broaden the geographic base** of financial partners while deepening cooperation with the EU.

ⁱ Initial commitments from the German government to implement Hintco's double-sided auction mechanism included €300 million for the 2024 ammonia pilot auction—awarded to a project based in Egypt—and €587 million dedicated to the Africa lot in Hintco's second auction round.

- Funding structures must evolve beyond simple grants and loans toward **more catalytic financial instruments**—including blended-finance vehicles, guarantee mechanisms, and structured offtake agreements—to mitigate risk and mobilize private investment.
- **Expanding technical assistance and early-stage project development finance** is essential, as early-phase costs can reach several million euros and often represent a major bottleneck for African project developers.

Overall, the report concludes that Africa holds significant potential to develop a robust clean hydrogen sector, yet realizing this opportunity will require a shift in project design, targeted de-risking instruments, and broader international financial engagement. Strengthening early-stage support and fostering domestic value chains will be essential to unlock investment, accelerate project maturity, and ensure that Africa can meaningfully participate in the global hydrogen economy.

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The hydrogen opportunity: Status of clean hydrogen production projects globally

Clean hydrogen is emerging as a cornerstone of global green industrial development efforts. An indicator of progress in this field is the status of clean hydrogen production projects currently under development.

According to the IEA's latest database release¹, 2,618 clean hydrogen projects are being tracked worldwide, representing a total planned production capacity of 218 Mtpa-H₂. Among these, 599 projects have reached a final investment decision (FID) or are already under construction or in operation. However, their combined production output amounts to only 7 Mtpa-H₂ — about 3% of the global project pipeline.

Projects that have advanced beyond FID are concentrated primarily in the Global North, notably in North America, Europe; in the Middle East, and in Asia (including China, South Korea, Japan, and India).

Also, countries in Africa, Latin America, and Southeast Asia show strong ambitions to enter the emerging clean hydrogen market, with a growing pipeline of predominantly export-oriented projects. Yet, this pipeline remains at an early stage of maturity.

Focusing on Africa, only three projects have reached FID, and five are operational, out of a total of 122 projects listed in the IEA database. The scale of these ambitions is reflected in project size: the average planned production capacity in Africa stands at 369 ktpa-H₂, compared to a global average of 94 ktpa-H₂.

This report examines the key characteristics of successful clean hydrogen project development, drawing on an analysis of the projects in the IEA database that have advanced beyond FID. The findings provide insights into pathways for more effective project development in emerging and developing countries, particularly in Africa, to help narrow the gap with developed countries.

Figure 1: Global overview of clean hydrogen production projects based on IEA database.¹

Global investments in clean hydrogen: A fraction of a fraction goes to African countries

Bloomberg New Energy Finance (BNEF) reports that global investments in clean energy reached USD 2,084 billion in 2024.² Of this total, investments in clean hydrogen — primarily in electrolyzer installations — accounted for only USD 8 billion, representing less than 1% of overall clean energy investment. In Africa, investments in electrolyzers for clean hydrogen production amounted to merely USD 13 million.

These figures underscore a striking imbalance: despite ambitious project pipelines, actual investment commitments remain limited — both globally and particularly in Africa.

In October 2025, H2Global hosted a stakeholder workshop with energy finance experts from across Africa during the World PtX Summit in Morocco [WHITE PAPER PtX Summit 2025]. The discussions highlighted three key factors for the successful development of clean hydrogen projects:

1. Long-term offtake agreements with reliable counterparties;
2. Robust risk management, regulatory clarity, and political support;
3. A strong domestic project anchor that fosters regional value chains, local employment, and community buy-in.

Together, these factors address two central dimensions that frame this report: risk and opportunity. Accordingly, this report adopts a quantitative approach to explore how investment decisions in successful clean hydrogen projects are shaped by these factors of risk and opportunity. It seeks to answer the guiding question: What enabling conditions foster and sustain successful clean hydrogen project development?

Figure 2: Global investments in clean energy by technology based on Bloomberg New Energy Finance (BNEF).²

Methodology: Analyzing success factors for clean hydrogen projects

To identify the enabling conditions for successful clean hydrogen projects, this report adopts a data-driven analytical framework (illustrated on the right). The foundation of this approach is the 2025 release of the IEA database of clean hydrogen production projects¹, which is enriched with additional data obtained through AI-assisted desk research. Supplementary indicators include country-level metrics on production costs of renewable electricity, economic strengths and hydrogen-related opportunities, as well as various risk dimensions (financial, political, climate change, and water). At the project level, further attributes capture investor profiles and offtake structures.

The consolidated dataset is analyzed using several clustering algorithms—k-means, Gaussian mixture models, DBSCAN, and agglomerative clustering—across configurations of two to ten clusters.

Subsequent statistical analysis identifies key factors characterizing each cluster and their relevance for project success. These cluster characteristics are then compared to the project pipeline in African countries to derive targeted support instruments that address specific challenges and capitalize on regional opportunities.

Figure 3: Research methodology to identify successful pathways for clean hydrogen project development.

Explaining investments through factors of risk and opportunity

Two key dimensions shape risk—return profiles of clean hydrogen projects and corresponding investment decisions: robust risk management, particularly regarding the offtake of clean hydrogen products, and the presence of a domestic project anchor that enables regional value creation. This report seeks to explain final investment decisions (FIDs) on clean hydrogen projects by quantifying the interplay of associated risks and opportunities (as illustrated on the right).

Opportunity factors include the *Decarbonization Technology Strength (DTS)* and *Decarbonization Technology Opportunity (DTO)* indices^{3,4}, derived from the *Harvard Atlas of Economic Complexity*⁵. Both indices are calculated relative to a basket of goods relevant to clean hydrogen value chains. DTS reflects a country’s current capability to produce these goods, while DTO captures its potential to develop such capabilities based on related industrial output. Together, these indices describe domestic economic opportunities and are linked to a project’s market orientation, i.e., whether it targets export markets or domestic offtake.

Another crucial determinant is the renewable energy production potential based on open-source data from EWI Cologne⁶. At the project level, the dataset captures whether sponsors have a strategic interest in the project (for example, securing a position within the hydrogen value chain). A related indicator records whether a sponsor also acts as an offtaker, directly mitigating offtake-related risks.

Risk factors encompass the country risk premium⁷, water risk⁸, and the OECD country risk index⁹ (as a proxy for political stability), along with climate risk¹⁰. The first three typically exert a negative influence on investment decisions, while elevated climate risk may, conversely, in some circumstances, strengthen political will and accelerate investment by prioritizing national resilience and decarbonization efforts.

Opportunities	Risks
Decarbonization Technology Opportunity Index	Financial: Country risk premium
Decarbonization Technology Strength Index	Environmental: Climate risk
Offtake market orientation	Environmental: Water risk
Levelized cost of electricity	Political: OECD country risk
Sponsor: Offtaker	
Sponsor: Strategic	

Figure 4: Opportunity and risk factors considered for clustering.

Results of the clustering analysis: Four key success pathways

The clustering analysis looks at successful projects, i.e. being operational or with FID, from IEA's global database of clean hydrogen production projects¹.

Agglomerative clustering with four cluster centers is identified as the most suitable model configuration. This setup represents a compromise between clustering quality—measured through standard metrics, i.e. the silhouette score¹¹, Davies—Bouldin index¹², and Calinski—Harabasz index¹³—and the interpretability of the resulting groups. The four clusters reveal distinct pathways for successful hydrogen project development:

- Cluster 1 — Export-oriented projects:** Comprising 8% of all successful projects, this cluster is characterized by a strong focus on export markets for clean hydrogen and its derivatives.
- Cluster 2 — Sponsor—offtaker integration:** Representing 16% of successful projects, these projects demonstrate strong vertical integration, with at least one project sponsor also serving as the offtaker of hydrogen-based products. This integration significantly mitigates offtake risk.
- Cluster 3 — Favorable economic and renewable conditions:** Accounting for 15% of successful projects, this cluster includes those located in host countries that combine **low country risk premiums** and **high industrial maturity** related to clean hydrogen (i.e., a high *DT Strength* score) with **abundant renewable energy potential**.
- Cluster 4 — Industrial growth and climate-driven opportunity:** Encompassing the remaining 62% of successful projects, this cluster is defined by host countries with **strong industrial growth potential** along the clean hydrogen value chain (high *DT Opportunity* score) and **heightened climate risk**, which collectively encourage more progressive policy environments and risk-tolerant investment behavior.

Cluster	Cluster size (%of all)	Market orientation	Sponsor is offtaker	Sponsor is strategic	DT Opportunity	DT Strength	Energy potential	Country risk premium	Climate risk	Water risk	OECD risk	cluster_size
1	8%	Export	0.04	0.96	0.33	0.56	0.43	0.25	0.24	0.57	0.30	45
2	16%	Domestic	1.00	1.00	0.37	0.32	0.11	0.16	0.38	0.42	0.10	89
3	15%	Domestic	0.00	1.00	0.25	0.74	0.74	0.07	0.12	0.55	0.14	84
4	62%	Domestic	0.02	0.83	0.36	0.33	0.04	0.15	0.39	0.42	0.06	351

Figure 5: Cluster average values of analyzed influencing factors on project success. Values are normalized on a scale from 0-1.

At the country level, favorable economic and renewable energy conditions (Cluster 3), as well as strong industrial growth potential and heightened climate-related risks (Cluster 4), create macro-environments that significantly increase the likelihood of project success. At the project level, participation in international markets (Cluster 1) and the integration of offtakers within the project consortium (Cluster 2) emerge as important enabling factors that help projects secure final investment decisions.

Cluster 1: Export-oriented projects

Projects in this cluster are predominantly large-scale, export-oriented initiatives, with an average installed electrolyzer capacity of approximately 200 MW_{el} and planned commissioning within the next few years. Their main products—ammonia and methanol—are globally traded commodities supported by well-established international markets and logistics infrastructures.

It is noteworthy, however, that such export-oriented projects account for only about 8% of all successful projects captured in the dataset. The remaining 92% primarily comprise smaller-scale, domestically focused projects, most of which are already operational. This indicates that export orientation and large-scale development are not success factors per se, but rather represent an emerging pathway in hydrogen production that is opening new global offtake opportunities. As the global clean hydrogen economy matures, a global market emerges, and hydrogen and its derivatives become internationally traded commodities, export-orientation of production projects will become a more common business model to de-risk offtake structures through global market participation. However, as a global market is currently not existing, this strategy remains a risky bet on the future and export-oriented projects remain dependent on bilateral offtake agreements.

Another salient observation across all successful clean hydrogen projects is the strong participation of strategic investors already active along the hydrogen value chain, as well as existing national hydrogen strategies¹⁴ in the host countries.

Representative examples from cluster 1 include the Da'an Renewable Hydrogen and Ammonia Project in Jilin, China, developed by Jilin Electric Power.¹⁵ The facility is already operational and integrates 800 MW of renewables with electrolysis to produce 32,000 t H₂ and 180,000 t NH₃ annually. Likewise, phase I of the Green Hydrogen and Chemicals project developed by ACME and SCATEC in Oman plans to produce 100,000 t NH₃ annually from an installed electrolysis capacity of 320 MW_{el}.¹⁶

Figure 6: Characteristic features of Cluster 1.

Cluster 2: Value chain integration

Projects in the second cluster are small-scale (~20 MWe), early-mover initiatives with a strong focus on domestic offtake. A defining feature of these projects is the active involvement of investors who also serve as offtakers, particularly in the mobility sector, but also in power generation, refining, and steel production.

This integration of production and offtake within a single consortium represents the core success factor of these projects. It reduces commercial risk and enables viable business models by leveraging synergies within regional industrial ecosystems, such as chemical parks or hydrogen refueling stations for commercial vehicle fleets.

Illustrative examples of this pathway include the Niagara Hydrogen Center in Canada, developed by *Atura Power*.¹⁷ The project deploys a 20 MW electrolyzer using hydroelectric power from Niagara Falls to supply low-carbon hydrogen for local industrial and mobility offtakers, exemplifying a tightly integrated, regionally focused value chain. Similarly, Germany's HyBit Project in Bremen, led by *ArcelorMittal*, integrates a 54 MW electrolyzer to produce hydrogen for direct-reduced iron (DRI) steelmaking, with on-site consumption ensuring stable demand.¹⁸ Both projects demonstrate how local integration of production and use underpins commercially viable early-mover models.

Figure 7: Characteristic features of Cluster 2.

Cluster 3: Favorable economic and renewable conditions

Projects in the third cluster are mid-scale (~50 MWeI) and resemble those in the second cluster in that they are early-mover initiatives focused on domestic offtake, primarily within the mobility sector. Their distinction lies in the host country’s enabling environment: These projects are situated in economies that demonstrate high industrial maturity related to clean hydrogen (i.e., a high *DT Strength* score), coupled with a low country risk premium and abundant renewable energy potential. The convergence of these factors establishes a particularly favorable investment climate for clean hydrogen development.

Illustrative examples of this pathway include Plug Power’s Green Hydrogen Plant¹⁹ in Camden County, Georgia, United States and the Mongolia Ordos Otog Front Banner

Shanghaimiao Hydrogen and Solar Energy Complex²⁰ in China. The Camden County facility, with an electrolyzer capacity of around 45 MW, produces up to 15 tons of green hydrogen per day powered by renewable electricity for domestic mobility and industrial applications across the southeastern United States. The Shanghaimiao complex in China combines large-scale solar generation with electrolytic hydrogen production to supply regional industrial and mobility demand. Both projects exemplify domestically oriented, early-mover initiatives situated in favorable economic environments with high renewable potential, reflecting the defining characteristics of Cluster 3.

Figure 8: Characteristic features of Cluster 3.

Cluster 4: Industrial growth and climate-driven opportunity

The fourth cluster comprises 62% of all successful clean hydrogen projects identified in the dataset. These projects are typically small-scale (~10 MW_{el}) developments with offtake primarily directed toward domestic mobility and power sectors. They are predominantly located in countries exhibiting strong industrial growth potential related to clean hydrogen and heightened exposure to climate risks. The combination of these factors fosters both market-driven and policy-driven momentum: industrial growth prospects attract investment from domestic stakeholders, while policymakers are incentivized to establish supportive frameworks and targeted incentives that facilitate gradual sectoral expansion. Although climate-related risks do not directly shape the business case of individual projects, they contribute to a more risk-tolerant investment environment and promote progressive policymaking that accelerates the overall development of the clean hydrogen sector.

Examples of this cluster include White Martins' Green Hydrogen Plant in Jacareí, São Paulo²¹, and the Fukushima Hydrogen Energy Research Field in Japan²². The Jacareí facility, operated by White Martins (a Linde company), features an electrolyzer capacity of around 5 MW, producing approximately 400 kilograms of low-carbon hydrogen per day. The plant supplies industrial clients and local mobility applications, contributing to Brazil's emerging clean hydrogen ecosystem. In Japan, the Fukushima Hydrogen Energy Research Field is supplying a local hydrogen refueling station with an installed electrolysis capacity of 10 MW_{el}. Both developments exemplify small-scale, domestically oriented projects situated in industrially dynamic regions with growing climate exposure, aligning closely with the defining characteristics of Cluster 4.

Figure 9: Characteristic features of Cluster 4.

Benchmarking Africa's clean hydrogen projects against four success pathways

As outlined above, the clean hydrogen project pipeline in Africa remains less mature compared to the global project pipeline: In Northern Africa, 64 projects have been announced, while 58 are under development in sub-Saharan Africa. Of these, only eight projects have progressed beyond final investment decision (FID). Comparing the characteristics of these projects with the four success clusters provides valuable insights into the underlying reasons for this disparity.¹

Offtake orientation: Among the successful clean hydrogen projects in the analyzed database, 92% are oriented toward domestic or regional offtake opportunities. In contrast, 89% of projects in Northern Africa and 76% in sub-Saharan Africa are primarily export-oriented. This strong export focus reflects a strategic bet on the future global ramp-up of clean hydrogen demand and familiar commodity-driven business models, but it also exposes projects to significant offtake risk. Such risk constitutes a major barrier to the maturation of African hydrogen projects.

Value chain integration: 17% of successful projects exhibit vertical integration across the value chain, with a project sponsor also acting as an offtaker—substantially reducing offtake risk. In Africa, however, this share is markedly lower: only 5% of projects in Northern Africa show such integration, and none in sub-Saharan Africa. This lack of domestic or regional offtake capacity further amplifies the offtake risk that African clean hydrogen projects are facing.

Strong conditions: A third success factor is the presence of favorable economic conditions—namely, a combination of industrial maturity, low country risk premiums, and abundant renewable energy potential. While African nations possess vast renewable energy resources, they generally face less favorable investment conditions due to elevated country risk premiums and limited industrial maturity. In turn, this leads to elevated financing costs and lower foreign direct investment.

Economic opportunity and environmental risk: The fourth success cluster is characterized by robust industrial growth potential along the clean hydrogen value chain, coupled with increased climate risk that fosters more risk-tolerant investment behavior and progressive policymaking. These conditions are also present in many African countries where hydrogen projects are emerging.

African clean hydrogen projects could mitigate their heightened offtake risk through a complementary focus on domestic and regional offtake opportunities and by pursuing greater value chain integration. Both strategies align with the strong industrial growth potential observed in the analyzed African economies. To address the inherent macroeconomic risks and the low levels of foreign direct investments, tailored financial support instruments will be essential. Both issues are discussed in greater detail in the following sections of the report.

Financing an archetypal 100 MWe clean hydrogen project

The total investment cost for an archetypal clean hydrogen project with an installed electrolyzer capacity of 100 MWe can reach up to €400 million.²³ However, this full amount is not required during the construction phase alone. Significant capital is already needed during the early development phases of the project.

During the concept, pre-Front-End Engineering and Design (FEED), and FEED stages, projects typically require €10–100 million before reaching the final investment decision (FID).²⁴ During these stages, financing generally comes from equity investors (project sponsors, venture capital funds) or from concessional sources. Because the project outcome is still uncertain, this capital is considered high-risk. Limited access to such high-risk funding in many African countries creates substantial barriers for project developers and contributes to the immaturity of the clean hydrogen pipeline on the continent. Concessional financing options that could alleviate this gap remain scarce.

To reach FID, projects must secure substantial debt financing (bank loans, project bonds, private debt). Debt providers require lower risk exposure, which in turn demands strong de-risking measures and secure offtake agreements. For many African clean hydrogen projects, challenging macroeconomic environments and the absence of creditworthy offtakers hinder access to debt. As an alternative, lenders may require a higher equity share as risk compensation—raising overall financing costs.

The analysis of a typical financing structure across the development stages of a clean hydrogen project highlights critical gaps both in the early development phases and in the lead-up to securing FID. Addressing these challenges will require tailored financial support instruments that can de-risk projects, mobilize capital, and enable the successful development of clean hydrogen projects in Africa.

Figure 10: Overview of financing needs and potential sources of finance across project development stages for an archetypal 100 MWe clean hydrogen project.

Financial support instruments for clean hydrogen in Africa: Overview

Total financial support currently targeted toward the development of clean hydrogen projects in Africa amounts to **€4 billion**, based on an updated analysis of a database published by GIZ in May 2025.²⁵ This figure stands in stark contrast to the USD 222 billion (€192 billion) in available clean-hydrogen funding for the rest of the world in 2025, as estimated by BNEF.²⁶ Moreover, only 20% of the committed financial support in Africa has been disbursed to date, highlighting persistent bottlenecks in fund distribution, limited project readiness, and a shortage of investable hydrogen projects across the continent. Financial support for clean hydrogen in Africa is predominantly driven by EU-based institutions and governments, which account for 78% (approximately €3.1 billion) of all available funding. At the European level, key actors include the European Investment Bank (EIB)—providing a mix of grants, concessional loans, and technical assistance—and the broader EU Global Gateway initiative, designed as a multi-instrument platform to mobilize additional private capital. Germany emerges as the single most significant contributor of funds, primarily through the H2Global double auction mechanism (with €887 million committedⁱⁱ) and the national development bank KfW, including its PtX Platform. Alongside these European actors, the Climate Investment Funds (CIF) represent an important multilateral source of concessional finance supporting Africa’s emerging hydrogen sector. Within Africa itself, three major national investment vehicles—the Sovereign Fund of Egypt, the SDG Namibia One Fund, and the South Africa-H2 Fund—have begun to play a significant role as equity providers for domestic clean-hydrogen projects. Notably, the Namibian and South African funds are structured as blended-finance vehicles supported by national governments and the EU, with the explicit aim of leveraging private capital.

ⁱⁱ Initial commitments from the German government to implement Hintco’s double-sided auction mechanism included €300 million for the 2024 ammonia pilot auction—awarded to a project based in Egypt—and €587 million dedicated to the Africa lot in Hintco’s second auction round.

Financial support instruments for clean hydrogen in Africa: Findings

Four key findings emerge from this analysis of Africa's hydrogen-finance landscape. First, the strong dominance of EU-based funding (78%) suggests considerable room to diversify the geographical base of financial support, which would help increase the total available funding. Second, the low disbursement rate of just 20% reflects a potential mismatch between available capital and project readiness. Many projects remain at an early stage of development and are not yet able to meet donor requirements, underscoring the need for stronger early-stage support mechanisms. Third, simple loans and grant together represent 37% of available support. Meanwhile, more catalytic instruments, such as blended-finance structures or contract-for-difference schemes, remain underused despite their potential to mobilize significant private investment. A greater emphasis on such instruments would increase the effectiveness and leverage of concessional funds. Finally, pre-FID financial support, such as technical assistance grants, represent only below two percent of total available support. Yet such early-stage support is indispensable during initial development phases, where costs can quickly reach several million euros and require scarce high-risk equity. Strengthening these early-stage support mechanisms would substantially improve project maturity across African hydrogen pipelines and facilitate more efficient deployment of financial resources in later development stages.

78%
share of EU-based funds

20%
share of disbursed funds

37%
share of simple support
through grants and loans

< 2%
share of pre-FID
financial support

Recommendations

The report identifies four pathways that have thus far resulted in successful clean hydrogen project development: (1) export orientation, (2) value chain integration as project-level characteristics, and (3) favorable economic and renewable resource conditions as well as (3) industrial growth and climate-related opportunities as country-level drivers. Clean hydrogen projects announced in Africa are primarily export-oriented, with limited local value chain integration. This pattern reflects a replication of established commodity-driven business models, existing infrastructure geared towards export, and a strong dependence on foreign capital—factors that collectively reinforce export-focused project structures. The report's analysis of successful project pathways is integrated with a financial overview of Africa's clean hydrogen sector, highlighting three structural characteristics: concentration of funding from EU-based sources, persistent low disbursements, and scarce financial support during early development phases. These insights point to two main areas of recommendation:

Building a domestic anchor. The emerging clean hydrogen market is marked by two defining features: non-transparent pricing, due to the absence of price indices or public markets, and a persistent gap between production costs and market willingness to pay. A strong reliance on export markets heightens the risks associated with these uncertainties and often results in projects stalling at early development stages due to missing offtake agreements. In contrast, domestic or regional value chain integration can help mitigate these shortcomings by leveraging local synergies such as reduced infrastructure needs, established business relationships, and shared strategic interests. In Africa, however, developing a domestic anchor is more difficult than in other regions due to comparatively weaker local markets for clean hydrogen. However, regional cooperation and an initial focus on certain sectors, such as fertilizers and steel, offer promising avenues to anchor domestic demand. Establishing a domestic anchor not only improves project viability but also promotes more sustainable socio-economic development within the region.

Using tailored financial support instruments in three steps. First, African countries should broaden the geographical base of financial support while continuing to deepen partnerships with the EU. Second, international financial institutions should complement simple funding structures with more targeted and catalytic instruments. This includes embedding grants and concessional loans into blended-finance vehicles and innovative mechanisms like double auctions to mobilize greater private investment, while also strengthening guarantee instruments that help de-risk projects approaching final investment decisions. Expanding technical assistance will further enhance project maturity and enable more effective disbursement of available funds. Together, these measures would help accelerate project development and improve the overall effectiveness of clean hydrogen financing in Africa.

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